

Supplemental Figure S1: Deep brain stimulation lead locations of study participants.

Lead trajectories from DN DBS clinical trial participants from whom SSEPs were collected overlaid on the 92% confidence dentate. MRI and CT scans were first co-registered in each participant and the segmented DNs of all participants were aligned relative to their principal axes (inferior to superior, I to S; posterior to anterior, P to A; lateral to medial, L to M). The 92% confidence dentate represents correspondence of dentate segmentation in at least 11 of 12 participants in the clinical trial and is modeled as a translucent grey hull. The lead trajectories are shown as colored lines. Each dot represents the location of one of the electrode contacts along the lead. For participants implanted with directional leads, note that the radially arranged set of contacts are simplified and represented as a single dot.

Supplemental Figure S2: Overview of preprocessing steps for the timing paradigm. The traces above outline the preprocessing steps used for when the timing of DBS relative to median nerve stimulation was varied. The black trace in the top left shows an example of an SSEP recorded with DBS delivery 5 ms after median nerve stimulation. First, the median nerve stimulation artifact (blue arrow) and DBS stimulation artifact (red arrow) were blanked via linear interpolation. Next, after re-referencing, the evoked response from DBS alone (red trace) was time-shifted and subtracted from the SSEP to compensate for additive EEG from the DBS pulse.

Supplemental Table S1: Continuous Dentate Nucleus Deep Brain Stimulation Parameters During Single Pulse Somatosensory Evoked Potential Recording.

Participant Code	Lead Type	Cathode	Anode	Pulsewidth (μ sec)	LF DBS Pulse Amplitude (mV)	HF DBS Pulse Amplitude (mV)	SSEP Rate (Hz)
003	ND	4/5/6	7/8	90	6.0	6.0	3.1
004	D	8	5/6/7	90	6.0	4.0	4.1
005	D	2/3/4	5/6/7	90	4.0	4.0	3.1
007	D	2/3/4	5/6/7	100	3.0	3.0	4.3
008	D	2/3/4/5/6/7	8	90	6.0	6.0	4.3
010	D	1/2/3/4	8	90	6.0	6.0	2.7
013	ND	5/6	8	90	6.0	4.0	2.7
014	ND	4/5	8	90	7.5	1.2	2.7
015	ND	2/3/4	8	90	6.0	1.1	2.7

ND, non-directional Vercise Standard DBS lead (Boston Scientific, Marlborough, USA); D, directional Vercise Cartesia™ lead; LF, low frequency; DBS, deep brain stimulation; HF, high frequency; SSEP, somatosensory evoked potential. Anode and cathode numbers refer to Boston Scientific's numbering scheme, with 1 referring to the most distal contact and 8 being the most proximal along the lead. Multiple anodal or cathodal contacts separated by slashes means that these contacts were used in parallel as anode/cathode during stimulation.

Supplemental Table S2: Continuous Dentate Nucleus Deep Brain Stimulation Parameters During Paired Pulse Somatosensory Evoked Potential Recording

Participant Code	Cathode	Anode	Pulsewidth (μ sec)	LF DBS Pulse Amplitude (mV)	HF DBS Pulse Amplitude (mV)	SSEP Rate (Hz)	Inter-Pulse Interval (ms)
008	2/3/4/5/6/7	8	90	4.0	4.0	2.8	30
010	1/2/3/4	8	90	6.0	4.0	2.7	40
011	4/5/6	8	90	9.0	9.0	n/a	40
013	4/5	7/8	120	2.0	2.0	2.8	40
014	4/5	8	90	7.5	0.6	2.7	40
015	2/3/4	8	90	6.0	1.1	2.7	40

LF DBS, low frequency; DBS, deep brain stimulation; HF, high frequency; SSEP, somatosensory evoked potential. Anode and cathode numbers refer to Boston Scientific's numbering scheme, with 1 referring to the most distal contact and 8 being the most proximal along the lead. Multiple anodal or cathodal contacts separated by slashes means that these contacts were used in parallel as anode/cathode during stimulation.

Supplemental Table S3: Deep Brain Stimulation Parameters During Paired DBS and Somatosensory Evoked Potential Recording

Participant Code	Cathode	Anode	Pulsewidth (μ sec)	Pulse Amplitude (mA)	SSEP Rate (Hz)
007	2/3/4	5/6/7	100	3.0	4.3
010	2/3/4/5/6/7	8	200	1.5	4.3
011 (X1)	4/5	6/7	200	4.0	2.8
011 (X2)	4/5/6	8	90	6.0	2.8
013	5/6	8	90	6.0	2.8
014	4/5	8	90	6.0	2.8

X1, first lead externalization; X2, second lead externalization. Anode and cathode numbers refer to Boston Scientific's numbering scheme, with 1 referring to the most distal contact and 8 being the most proximal along the lead. Multiple anodal or cathodal contacts separated by slashes means that these contacts were used in parallel as anode/cathode during stimulation.